

THE PERENNIAL PHILOSOPHY OF YOGA

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Introduction

Yoga philosophy is one of the six major orthodox schools of Hinduism. Ancient, medieval and most modern literature often refers to Yoga school of Hinduism simply as Yoga. It is closely related to the Samkhya school of Hinduism. Yoga school's systematic studies to better oneself physically, mentally and spiritually has influenced all other schools of Indian philosophies. The Yoga Sutras of Patanjali is a key text of the Yoga school of Hinduism.

The epistemology of Yoga school of Hinduism, like Sāmkhya School, relies on three of six Pramanas, as the means of gaining reliable knowledge. These included Pratyakṣa (perception), Anumāṇa (inference) and Sabda (Āptavacana, word/testimony of reliable sources). The metaphysics of Yoga is built on the same dualist foundation as the Samkhya school.[6] The universe is conceptualized as of two realities in Samkhya-Yoga schools: Puruṣa (consciousness) and prakṛiti (matter). Jiva (a living being) is considered as a state in which puruṣa is bonded to prakṛiti in some form, in various permutations and combinations of various elements, senses, feelings, activity and mind. During the state of imbalance or ignorance, one of more constituents overwhelm the others, creating a form of bondage. The end of this bondage is called liberation, or moksha by both Yoga and Samkhya school of Hinduism. The ethical theory of Yoga school is based on Yamas and Niyama, as well as elements of the Guṇa theory of Samkhya.

Yoga school of Hinduism differs from the closely related non-theistic/atheistic Samkhya school by incorporating the concept of a "personal, yet essentially inactive, deity" or "personal god" (Ishvara). Samkhya school suggests that jnana (knowledge) is a sufficient means to moksha, Yoga school suggests that systematic techniques/practice (personal experimentation) combined

with Samkhya's approach to knowledge is the path to moksha. Yoga shares several central ideas with Advaita Vedanta school of Hinduism, with the difference that Yoga philosophy is a form of experimental mysticism, while Advaita Vedanta is a form of monistic personalism. Advaita Vedanta, and other schools of Hinduism, accept, adopt and build upon many of the teachings and techniques of Yoga.

The systematic collection of ideas of Yoga school of Hinduism is found in the Yoga Sutras of Patanjali. After its circulation in the first half of 1st millennium CE, many Indian scholars reviewed it, then published their Bhāṣya (notes and commentary) on it, which together form a canon of texts called the Pātañjalayogaśāstra ("The Treatise on Yoga of Patañjali").

Six darsanas :

The Yoga school of Hinduism has been included as one of its six orthodox schools in medieval era Indian texts. The other schools are Samkhya, Nyaya, Vaisheshika, Mimamsa and Vedanta. The Yoga school of Hindu philosophy is most closely related to the Samkhya School. In both, the foundational concepts include two realities: *Purusha* and *Prakriti*. The *Purushais* defined as that reality which is pure consciousness and is devoid of thoughts or qualities. The *Prakriti* is the empirical, phenomenal reality which includes matter and also mind, sensory organs and the sense of identity (self, soul). A living being is held in both schools to be the union of matter and mind. The Yoga school differs from the Samkhya School in its views on the ontology of *Purusha*, on axiology and on soteriology

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Debashish Banerji, 1982;

Structure and Process: Integral Philosophy and Triple Transformation, Vol. 1, Pg.no. 18. He quotes that

Integral Yoga” lays out a process of psychological integration. In his own practice of this process, we find the use of disciplines and goals belonging to a number of Indian spiritual traditions, particularly those related to certain schools of Vaishnavism and Tantra, along with practices taken from the Bhagavad Gita, an older Vedanta and the Veda. On the face of it, this may seem like another instance of the attempt to structure an inclusivistic organization of consciousness, as with Wilber. But the traditions from which Sri Aurobindo developed his transformative psychology can be seen to continue in forms which further their own cultural history in his practice. Moreover, they are not used in an additive way as components towards something which includes them, rather each one may be seen.

David Gordon White, 1973;

Yoga, Brief History of an Idea, Vol. 2, Pg. no.34. He quotes that

Yoga is an analysis of the dysfunctional nature of everyday perception and cognition, which lies at the root of suffering, the existential conundrum whose solution is the goal of Indian philosophy. Once one comprehends the cause(s) of the problem, one can solve it through philosophical analysis combined with meditative practice.

At bottom, India's many yoga traditions are soteriologies, doctrines of salvation, concerning the attainment of release from suffering existence and the cycle of rebirths (samsāra). The problem of suffering existence and the allied doctrine of cyclic rebirth emerges about five centuries before the beginning of the Common Era, in the early Upanisads as well as the original teachings of the Jain founder Mahāvīra and the Buddhist founder Gautama Buddha.

Shri K. Pattabhi Jois, 1992;

An Introduction to the Fundamentals of Astanga Yoga, Jois Yoga, Vol. 1, Pg. no. 56. He quotes that

The method of asana practice prescribed by Shri K. Pattabhi Jois was taught to him by his teacher, Shri T. Krishnamacharya, and is said to have come from an ancient text, the Yoga Korunta. It relies on the linking of asanas through prescribed vinyasas (movements) and incorporates deep, even breathing and steady gazing with the eyes, or drsti. The 'vinyasa,' or movement between asanas, encourages the blood to circulate properly in the body, while the deep breathing supplies a rich source of pure air, oxygenating the blood and allowing the removal of unwanted toxins through the lungs. Internal heat is produced, and is described as burning up the impurities in the body, the toxins are liberated from the tissues by each asana.

Larson, Gerald James, 1989;

Classical Yoga as Neo-Samkhya: The history of Indian philosophy, Vol. 2. Pg. no. 41. He quotes that

Whereas classical Sāmkhya speaks of the thirteenfold instrument wrapped, as it were, in the five subtle elements, as the "eighteenfold" subtle body (sūksma-sarira) that transmigrates at death to a new rebirth body, the simpler and more sophisticated Yoga view is that if the citta is all-pervasive, at the moment of death, there is an immediate transference to a new embodiment, hence, obviating a need for a subtle body. Here again the parallel with Buddhist (and Jain) discussions is obvious, with the Theravādins (and classical Jain thought) like the Yoga philosophy arguing that there is no need for a subtle body (antarābhāva), and with the Sarvāstivādins and other Buddhist schools arguing for some sort of subtle body. Interestingly,

on this point, the Abhidharmakosa discussion comes out closer to the old Sāmkhya view of a need for a subtle body in contrast to the Yoga view which appears to relate to the Theravāda (and Jain) rejection of a subtle body.

Sri Swami Chidananda, 1991;

The Philosophy, Psychology & Practice of Yoga, Divine Life Society Publication, Vol. 1, Pg. no. 66. He quotes that

Yoga philosophy offers the analogy of a perfectly clear crystal which is transparent and pure, but becomes filled as it were with some colour if some coloured object is brought forth near it. The object thus brought forth may be a green-colored ball or a little red-coloured flower or a blue-coloured cork and the whole crystal becomes green or red or blue. This proximity of something having some characteristic brings about a seeming transference of that characteristic from that something into the pure, transparent, clear crystal. So, it is the proximity to something that is the cause for the apparent change in the otherwise attribute less crystal ball. Now, Yoga philosophy says that you are also in a similar state of proximity to something, you have become involved with something, and therefore, states and conditions that exist in that factor seem as though they have come and taken possession of you.

Professor Russell Kirkland, 1997;

Samkhya & Yoga: Two Classical Hindu "Paths of Insight". Department of Religion, University of Georgia, Pg. no. 23. He quotes that

Samkhya is often called a "dualist" philosophy, because it asserts a fundamental difference between what Westerners tend to regard as matter and spirit. But one must bear in mind that the basic Samkhya categories of purusha and prakriti do not really correspond to the Western categories of "matter" and "spirit." We would be much closer if we called purusha "subject(s)" and prakriti "object(s)." Purusha corresponds fairly well to the Western concept of "soul," while prakriti simply means everything other than "soul." Samkhya also recognizes the multiplicity of subjects or souls: each individual is ultimately a separate subject. In their natural state, each purusha is totally isolated from each other and from everything else. But at the moment, all purushas find themselves merged with elements of the alien reality called prakriti (object), and fail to realize that they are essentially distinct from it. That confusion of purusha and prakriti constitutes the state of bondage (samsara). Liberation (moksha) consists in the unravelling of this temporal union by realizing that the subject or soul (purusha) is truly different from the object or non-soul (prakriti).

Conclusion

Criticisms

Friedrich Nietzsche held that the idea that to treat others as more important than oneself is degrading and demeaning to the self. He also believed that the idea that others have a higher value than oneself hinders the individual's pursuit of self-development, excellence, and creativity. However, he did assert a "duty" to help those who are weaker than oneself.

David Kelley, discussing Ayn Rand's views, says that "there is no rational ground for asserting that sacrificing yourself in order to serve others is morally superior to pursuing your own (long-term, rational) self-interest. Altruism ultimately depends on non-rational 'rationales,' on mysticism in some form..." Furthermore, he holds that there is a danger of the state enforcing that moral ideal: "If self-sacrifice is an ideal - if service to others is the highest, most honorable course of action - why not force people to act accordingly?" He believes this can ultimately result in the state forcing everyone into a collectivist political system.

Norwegian eco-philosopher Arne Næss argues that environmental action based upon altruism — or service of the other — stems from a shrunken "egoic" concept of the self. Self-actualization will result, he argues, in the recovery of an "ecological self", in which actions formerly seen as altruistic are in reality a form of enlightened self-interest.

German philosopher Max Scheler distinguishes two different ways in which the strong can help the weak, one which is an expression of love, "motivated by a powerful feeling of security, strength, and inner salvation, of the invincible fullness of one's own life and existence" and another which is merely "one of the many modern substitutes for love, ... nothing but the urge to turn away from oneself and to lose oneself in other people's business." At its worst, Scheler says, "love for the small, the poor, the weak, and the oppressed is really disguised hatred, repressed envy, an impulse to detract, etc., directed against the opposite phenomena: wealth, strength, power, largesse."

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